

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROPER PATIENT MANAGEMENT DURING PSYCHIATRIC EMERGENCIES

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Introduction: Psychiatric emergencies are acute conditions involving mental disorders in aggravating states that present a significant risk to the patient themselves and the people around them. This type of emergency requires clinical intervention as soon as possible in order to prevent further damage. **Objective:** To highlight the importance of health professionals having the appropriate knowledge and skills to manage psychiatric emergencies correctly. **Methodology:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflective, descriptive and qualitative analysis. Eight articles from the journals Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) and Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature (LILACS) were used. **Results (Concluded):** The most serious conditions in psychiatric emergencies arise from: Substance abuse, psychotic outbreaks, suicidal ideation and attempted suicide; In these cases, emergency management involves a multidisciplinary approach, initially focused on the safety of the patient and others involved, and in more aggravating cases the technique of physical and mechanical restraint may be used by the team and in a humanized way, pharmacological interventions may be indicated to control acute symptoms in order to avoid the use of force, the dosage of the drug must be carefully monitored so that there are no adverse effects or pharmacological intoxication due to supra-physiological dosage. In the post-emergency period, specific planning is needed to control the patient through psychosocial interventions such as family support and psychotherapy. These treatments together play a fundamental role in stabilizing and preventing future crises, thus improving the quality of life of the patient and their family. **Final considerations:** The patient's history must be properly assessed so that both emergency and post-emergency management can be better approached; health professionals must have unequivocal knowledge of the management of psychiatric emergencies and must also provide family members with cohesive and logical information on how to act before, during and after the condition, improving the patient's prognosis with regard to future crises and enabling the family to provide the necessary support.

Keywords: Emergency. Assistance. Psychiatry.

Thematic Area: Management of the critically ill patient.